

IN-SERVICE TRAINING: ITS EFFECTS ON THE PROFESSIONAL GROWTH AND DEVELOPMENT OF ELEMENTARY TEACHERS

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In-Service Training: Its effects on the Professional Growth and Development of Elementary Teachers

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Abstract

In-service training plays an important role in the professional development of teachers, bridging the gap between traditional teaching methods and contemporary educational trends. The purpose of this study was to analyze the effectiveness of in-service training programs on the professional growth and development of the public elementary school teachers in Milagros district, Masbate. The training, mandated by R.A. No. 10533 (Basic Education Act of 2013) and Republic Act 10912 (Continuous Professional Development Law), aims to enhance teachers' pedagogical skills, classroom management, and subject knowledge to address the evolving educational demands. This research utilized a quantitative design, surveyed 50 elementary teachers to assess their profiles, the perceived benefits of various in-service training aspects, and the effects on both their professional development and student learnings. The data gathered were treated using the following statistical tool: frequency and percentage for the profiles of teachers, and weighted mean for the effects of in-service training to the teachers and learners. The findings revealed that teachers are predominantly young, with a majority holding Bachelor's degrees. The study found that the most valued aspects of in-service training are pedagogical skills, classroom management, assessment and evaluation, and subject expertise. However, technology and integration was identified as least emphasized. In-service training programs were perceived as very effective overall to the professional growth and development of teachers and as well as to the learning outcomes of the learners. The study concludes that while in service training is very useful, there are areas for further development. Sharing best practices and successful strategies from in-service training with other schools or districts will enhance overall educational outcomes.

Keywords: *In-service training, professional growth, professional development*

Introduction

In-service training is essential to teachers in developing themselves holistically and grows professionally. This way they will able to fill in the gaps from their old self to the new trend in the 21st century teaching and learning process. In-service training is a seminar workshop caters the needs of all teachers in improving their teaching methods and strategies, classroom management approaches, professional growth and development, and knowledge and skills enhancement towards uplifting student-centered learning. It provides ways to teachers in coping with the drastic change in the educational system from the transition of one curriculum to another. Hill and Ball (2015), indicated that teachers with little training have too little knowledge of the subjects they teach thus denying their students the most basic learning resources and this affects their teaching and learning.

Furthermore provisions of R.A No. 10533 otherwise known as The Basic Education Act of 2013 is to ensure that the enhanced basic education program meets the demand for quality teachers and school leaders, thus the DepEd in collaboration with the academe, and other institutions shall conduct an In-Service Training (INSET) on Content and Pedagogy. It focuses on keeping all teachers on track with the updated knowledge of subject areas believing that continuous learning both in content and instruction are important components of the teaching profession. In-service training can also change the attitude and skills of teachers and further increase the performance of students (Omar, C. M. Z. C. 2014). Teachers expose to many seminars and trainings tend to acquire more learning, get new ideas and technique and improve skills in delivering the lessons that will suit to learners diversity. Osamwonyi (2016) also states that lack of in service teacher training causes insufficient professional development of teachers and the enhances the gap between demands and actual success levels.

In 2019, Republic Act 10912, Continuous Professional Development Law, went into full effect, requiring teachers to earn Continuous Professional Development (CPD) units to keep their license to practice. Moreover, in-service trainings improve teachers' professional competencies as well as their beliefs, perceptions and attitudes towards the profession (Borg, 2011; Weinstein, 1989).

This proves that in-service training is an important element of teacher training system. With this the current study aims to determine the effects of in-service training program on the professional growth and development of public elementary school teachers. The results of the study could be fundamental in understanding the need to be developed on the part of the teachers and others.

Research Questions

More specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of teachers in terms of age, sex, educational attainment, length of service, training attended, and performance rating?
2. What specific aspects of In-service training are most beneficial for the professional growth and development of elementary

teachers?

3. What are the effects of In-service training on the professional growth and development of elementary teachers?
4. What are the effects of In-service training on the learning outcomes of learners as perceived by the teachers?

Literature Review

Professional Development

Professional development that supports co-teachers can increase co-teachers' abilities to collaborate effectively to provide innovative instruction that meets the needs of all learners in the classroom. (Goodhue, 2016). The training engenders change in human behavior, attitudes, knowledge, skills, and capabilities focused on cultivating professional etiquette required by teachers to perform adequately at given tasks (Guskey, 2014; Kabadayi, 2016).

Professional enhancement is essential to answer gaps in education systems. The low quality of education in the Philippines is the lack of competent teachers (Alvior, M. G., 2020).

In-Service Training

The primary purpose of INSET is to enable teachers to acquire new understanding and instructional skills (Quilapio, M. P., & Callo, E. C., 2022). It focuses on creating learning environments that enable teachers to develop their effectiveness in the classroom (Omar, 2014). It is the role of an effective school head to provide technical assistance to teachers and organizing and conducting in-service training programs (Delfino, 2023)

The main aspects of the in-service training for school teams valued by participants were: all topics covered systematically and coherently gave an excellent opportunity to focus on relevant issues, which should be considered in the schools' self-development activities in the field of IE; a practical approach to training structure helped to identify priority areas that need to be developed in particular schools; learning from each other both within their school team and across school teams contributed to finding the best solutions for meaningful implementation (Kivirand et al., 2021).

In the Department of Education (DepEd), twice a year of professional development activities called In-Service Training for Teachers (INSET) are planned by the department and organized per district. Every district in the entire archipelago holds this training every school year. This five-day annual and semesterly break training, approved by the DepEd, talks about current trends and issues in the Philippine education system. They invited experts and practitioners to help them bridge the gap in the perennial problem in the primary education curriculum. The goal of INSET is to educate teachers about national and regional programs that are tailored to the needs of the entire system to improve the professional growth of the teaching force, abreast of current trends and knowledge.

Methodology

Research Design

The researchers utilized a quantitative research design to examine the effects of In-Service training on the professional growth and development of elementary teachers from Milagros district. According to Bhandari (2020), Quantitative Research is the process of collecting and analyzing numerical data. It can be used to find patterns and averages, make predictions, test causal relationships, and generalize results to wider populations.

Respondents

This research used stratified random sampling, this method will ensure that different strata like different schools, and grade levels are represented. There are fifty (50) elementary teachers with different grade levels from Milagros district were the participants who were randomly chosen to participate in the study. The study's locale comprised the different elementary schools all situated in the district of Milagros, Masbate province.

Procedure

Before the questionnaire distribution, a letter asking for permission signed by the instructor, was sent to the Public Schools District Supervisor of Milagros, and the questionnaire was validated by the adviser and the dean to ensure their reliability. The researchers personally distributed the questionnaires together with the signed letter to the targeted respondents. The respondents and the researchers agreed on when to accomplish the questionnaire and its scheduled retrieval. Upon the retrieval of the 100% answered survey questionnaires, the data were analyzed and interpreted by getting the percentage of their responses.

Data Analysis

The data were carefully evaluated and analyzed using a percentage statistical tool.

Percentage. According to Calmorin (1997), a percentage is a way of expressing a proportion, a ratio, or a fraction in relation to a whole with 100 as a denominator.

Weighted Mean on the effects of In-service training on the professional growth and development of elementary teachers, and effects of In-service training on the learning outcomes of learners as perceived by the teachers.

Ethical Considerations

Before the distribution of the questionnaire in paper form, a signed letter of permission from the PSDS was sent to the principals to inform them about the survey to be conducted. Participants were given the right to withdraw from the study at any time without consequences. A self-made questionnaire checklist was used to gather data on the profile of teachers, aspects of In-service training, effects of In-service training on the professional growth and development of elementary teachers, and effects of In-service training on the learning outcomes of learners as perceived by the teachers. The data gathered are kept confidential, participants are remained anonymous, and the RA 10173 or the Data Privacy Act of 2012 is strictly followed.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. *Age Profile of the Teachers*

<i>Age Profile</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
51 and above	1	2
46-50	1	2
41-45	3	6
36-40	1	2
31-35	13	26
26-30	17	34
21-25	14	28
Total	50	100

A. Age

Table 1 indicates the age profile of the elementary teachers. It includes frequency and percentage. As indicated in the table, out of fifty teachers one or 2% were 51 year old and above; one or 2% belonged to 46-50 age bracket; three or 6% of the teachers belonged to the age bracket of 41-45; one or 2% belonged to the age bracket of 36-40; thirteen or 26% belonged to the age bracket of 31-35; seventeen or 34% belonged to the age bracket of 26-30; fourteen or 28% belonged to the age bracket of 21-25 years old.

The finding implies that majority of the elementary teachers from Milagros district were 26-30 years old. With this proportion of young teachers, professional growth and development should be given so that they can perform better and give their best for the better performance of the learners.

Table 2. *Sex Profile of the Teachers*

<i>Sex Profile</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Male	28	56
Female	22	44
Total	50	100

B. Sex

This table shows the sex profile of the teachers-respondents. It includes frequency and percentage. As shown in the table, out of fifty teachers, 28 or 56% were males, and 22 or 44% were females. Majority of these were males. The result implies that the slight male majority among teachers suggests a relatively balanced gender distribution which could positively impact role modeling, classroom management, and diversity in teaching approaches. According to Sokal & Katz (2008), the perception that male teachers may have a different approach to classroom management and discipline, particularly in handling boys' behavior. Their study also discusses how male teachers might use technology and other tools to engage boys in learning, which can influence the overall classroom environment.

Table 3. *Profile on Position Title of the Teachers*

<i>Position Title</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Teacher I	17	34
Teacher II	18	36
Teacher III	15	30
Master Teacher I	0	0
Total	50	100

C. Position Item

Table 3 indicates the position title of the elementary teachers from Milagros district. It includes frequency and percentage. As indicated in the table out of fifty teachers, 17 or 34% were Teacher I; 18 or 36% were Teacher II; 15 or 30% were Teacher III; and none or 0% were Master Teacher I.

The finding implies that school heads should motivate their teachers to raise their position title to the next higher level from Teacher I

to Teacher II, III and Master Teacher. Teachers should take extra steps to be aware of raising themselves.

Table 4. Profile of Educational Attainment of the Teachers

<i>Educational Attainment</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Full-fledged M.A	0	0
M.A. CAR	1	2
with units in M.A.	15	30
Graduate from another course with units in Education	2	4
BEEd Graduate	32	64
Total	50	100

D. Educational Attainment

Table 4 reflects the educational attainment profile of the elementary teachers from the district of Milagros. The table includes the frequency and percentage. As reflected in the table, none or 0% were full-fledged MA; 1 or 2% were M.A CAR; 15 or 30% with units in M.A; 2 or 4% graduated from another course with units in Education; and 32 or 64% were BEEd graduates.

Based on the findings majority of the elementary teachers from Milagros district were BEEd graduates, and none of them were M.A graduates but few have units in M.A.

The limited presence of advanced degrees among teachers may impact the depth and extent of teaching strategies and instructional qualities. According to Bakkenes & Wubbels (2010), the advanced degrees and continuous learning contribute to teachers' professional growth and leadership potential. Teachers with higher educational attainment are more likely to engage in innovative practices and take on leadership roles within the school, which is very important for school improvement.

Table 5. Profile on Length of Service of the Teachers

<i>Length of Service</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
10 years above	13	26
7-9	11	22
4-6	16	32
1-3	10	20
Total	50	100

E. Length of Service

Table 5 shows the profile of the length of service of the elementary teachers from the district of Milagros. The table includes the frequency and percentage. As shown in the table, 13 or 26% of the teachers had 10 years and above experience in teaching; 11 or 22% had 7-9 years of experience in teaching; 16 or 32% had 4-6 years of experience in teaching; and 10 or 20% had 1-3 years of experience in teaching. The finding shows that most of the elementary teachers in Milagros district have 4-6 years of experience in teaching, they are young in the service and need more experiences for better performance, and learners learning improvement.

The result shows the balanced distribution of teaching experience among teachers suggests a healthy mix over novice, mid-career, and experienced teachers within the district. According to Hargreaves and Fullan (2012), schools thrive when there is a combination of novice, mid-career, and experienced teachers. This diversity in experience creates opportunities for knowledge sharing, mentorship, and collaborative learning. Experienced teachers can provide guidance to newer teachers, while novice teachers may bring fresh perspectives and innovative teaching strategies to the group. Collaboration among teachers at different stages in their careers can significantly enhance teaching quality. Vangrieken et al. (2015) explain that teacher collaboration leads to better instructional practices, increases teacher confidence, and fosters continuous professional learning. In school with a range of teaching experience levels, this collaboration can become an essential part of professional development.

Table 6. Profile of Training Attended by the Teachers

<i>Training Attended</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Continuing Professional Development (CPD) Programs	12	24
Subject-Specific Training	10	20
Pedagogical Training	12	24
Curriculum Development	11	22
Mental Health	5	10
Total	50	100

F. Trainings Attended

Table 6 indicates the profile of training attended by the elementary teachers from Milagros district. The table includes the frequency and percentage. As shown in the table, 12 or 24 % of the teachers attended the Continuing Professional Development (CPD) Programs; 10 or 20% of the teachers attended the subject-specific training; 12 or 24% of the teachers attended pedagogical training; 11 or 22%

attended the curriculum development; and 5 or 10% of the teachers attended the mental health training.

The results show that there are trainings attended with nearly the same percentage aside from mental health training with only 10%. The variety of training attended by teachers indicates potential for professional growth, which can lead to improve instructional practices and students' learning outcomes. However, the relatively lower participation in certain areas, such as mental health, proposes opportunities for further development to ensure a comprehensive approach to education that addresses all aspects of student and teacher well-being. According to Reinke et al. (2011), mental health training for teachers is important, it helps them better support students' emotional and behavioral needs.

Table 7. Profile of Performance Ratings of the Teachers

<i>Performance Ratings</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Outstanding (O)	27	54
Very Satisfactory (VS)	21	42
Satisfactory (S)	2	4
Needs Improvement (NI)	0	0
Total	50	100

G. Performance Ratings

Table 7 shows the performance ratings of elementary teachers from Milagros district last school year 2022-2023. The table includes the frequency and percentage. As shown in the table, out of fifty teachers, 27 or 54% had "outstanding" performance ratings; 21 or 42% had a "very satisfactory" ratings; 2 or 4% had a "satisfactory" ratings, and none of the 50 elementary teachers from Milagros district received "needs improvement".

The results show that most of the respondents are performing very well. High performance ratings can significantly contribute to teacher's morale and motivation, leading to a more positive and productive work environment (Ryan & Deci, 2000). Those outstanding teachers are aspirants to any position higher than their present rank. School heads should encourage their teachers to improve their performance since this is one of the criteria needed for promotion.

Table 8. Aspects of In-Service Training

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Count</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
1. Pedagogical Skills	50	100
2. Technology and Integration	39	78
3. Professional Ethics	47	94
4. Inclusive Education	42	84
5. Classroom Management	50	100
6. Research and Innovation	43	86
7. Curriculum Updates and Enhancement	45	90
8. Policy Updates and Implementation	40	80
9. Assessment and Evaluation	50	100
10. Subject Expertise	50	100

Table 8 shows the aspects of In-Service Training. It includes the count and percentage. 50 or 100% of the respondents believed that the most emphasized aspects of in-service training are the Pedagogical Skills, Classroom Management, Assessment and Evaluation, and Subject Expertise. These are foundational skills for teachers, essential for ensuring that they can manage classrooms effectively, design appropriate assessments, and provide high-quality instruction. According to Darling-Hammond et al. (2017), effective in-service training should prioritize such core teaching competencies to improve student outcomes and enhance teacher effectiveness.

Technology and Integration is the least emphasized, with only 78% of the respondents selected it. Only 78% of the respondents believed that technology integration was adequately emphasized in in-service training suggests a significant gap in preparing teachers for the demands of a digital world. Schrum and Levin (2015) argue that technology has become a key component of 21st-century teaching and learning, and teachers must be well-versed in integrating technology into their classrooms to ensure that students develop the digital literacy skills they need to succeed. According to Mishra and Koehler's (2006) Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) framework, effective technology integration requires a strong interplay between technology, pedagogy, and content knowledge. If in-service training does not adequately cover the technological component, teachers may struggle to incorporate digital tools and approaches into their teaching practice, which could affect student engagement and learning outcomes.

Other important areas include Professional Ethics (94%), Inclusive Education (84%), Research and Innovation (86%), Curriculum Updates (90%), and Policy Updates (80%) received less attention. While these areas are covered to a degree, the variation in emphasis suggests that a more balanced approach to teacher development is needed. According to Desimone (2009), effective professional development should be comprehensive and address the diverse needs of teachers, ensuring that they are well-prepared for the various challenges they face in the classroom. In-service training that is overly focused on certain areas at the expense of others could leave teachers underprepared to handle important aspects of their professional responsibilities, such as implementing inclusive teaching strategies or staying informed about curriculum and policy changes. Moreover, the inclusion of topics such as research and innovation

is important for fostering a culture of continuous improvement and innovation in schools. Teachers who engaged in research-based practices are better equipped to refine their instructional strategies based on evidence of what works in their classrooms. According to Hattie (2009), teachers' engagement in research and reflection on their practices is one of the most effective ways to enhance student learning.

The results of the study highlight both strengths and areas for improvement in in-service training for teachers. While core competencies such as pedagogical skills, classroom management, and subject expertise are well-covered, the lower emphasis on technology integration reveals a gap that must be addressed, particularly in a rapidly digitizing world. Additionally, the variation in the emphasis placed on other important areas of professional development suggests a need for more balanced and comprehensive approach to ensure that teachers are fully prepared to meet the demands of modern education. By addressing these gaps, in-service training programs can better equip teachers to deliver high-quality instruction and support the diverse needs of their learners.

Table 9. Effects of In-Service Training on Teachers

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1. Improved Collaborative Teamwork	3.54	Very Effective	6
2. Better Adaptation to Curriculum Changes	3.58	Very Effective	5
3. Increased Awareness of Inclusive Education	3.22	Effective	10
4. Increased Confidence and Self-Efficacy	3.24	Effective	9
5. Enhanced Teaching Skills	3.7	Very Effective	4
6. Increased Technological Proficiency	3.34	Effective	8
7. Enhanced Classroom Management	3.94	Very Effective	1
8. Better Assessment Practices	3.88	Very Effective	2
9. Improved Content Knowledge	3.72	Very Effective	3
10. Strengthened Leadership Skills	3.5	Very Effective	7
Average Weighted Mean	3.56	Very Effective	

Table 9 shows the effects of in-service training on elementary teachers from Milagros district. It includes the weighted mean, interpretation and rank. As shown in the table, the effects of in-service training to teachers were given according to rank. Rank 1 was the enhanced classroom management with weighted mean of 3.94 interpreted as "very effective"; rank 2 was better assessment practices (3.88) interpreted as "very effective"; rank 3 with weighted mean of 3.72 is improved content knowledge interpreted as "very effective"; rank 4 was enhanced teaching skills (3.7) interpreted as "very effective"; rank 5 was better adaptation to curriculum changes (3.58) interpreted as "very effective"; rank 6 was improved collaborative teamwork (3.54) interpreted as "very effective"; rank 7 was strengthened leadership skills (3.5) interpreted as "very effective"; rank 8 was increased technological proficiency (3.34) interpreted as "effective"; rank 9 was increased confidence and self-efficacy (3.24) interpreted as "effective"; and rank 10 was increased awareness of inclusive education (3.22) interpreted as "effective".

The average weighted mean was 3.56 interpreted as "very effective". These demonstrate that in-service training programs are effective on various aspects of elementary teachers' professional growth and development in the Milagros district. The average weighted mean of 3.56, the in-service training programs are generally "very effective". The effectiveness of InSet in those areas as evidenced by the high average weighted mean, also reflects its alignment with the key principles of effective professional development.

According to Darling-Hammond et al. (2017), high quality professional development is one of the most important factors in improving teacher effectiveness. Successful professional development should be content-focused, involve active learning, and be aligned with teachers' needs and the school's goals (Desimone, 2009). The Milagros district's INSET programs seem to excel in these areas, particularly by providing teachers with the skills they need to manage classrooms and assess students effectively.

However, the results suggests that while they excel in enhancing classroom management, assessment practices, content knowledge, and teaching skills, there is a room for improvement in areas related to technology, teacher confidence, and inclusive education. Addressing these gaps could lead to more comprehensive professional development for teachers, and also to learners' performance.

Improving in-service training in the identified areas-technology integration, teacher confidence, and inclusive education could lead to more comprehensive professional development. Teachers who received more balanced training will be better equipped to use technology effectively, feel more confident in their teaching, and create more inclusive classrooms. This, in turn, could have positive effects on student performance.

Research shows that technology-rich classrooms improve student engagement and learning outcomes (Schrum & Levin, 2015). Similarly, when teachers are confident and able to differentiate instruction for diverse learners, student outcomes will improve (Hattie, 2009). Therefore, addressing these gaps in INSET could contribute to both teacher empowerment and student success.

The in-service training programs in the Milagros district have proven to be very effective in enhancing essential aspects of teaching, such as classroom management, assessment, content knowledge, and pedagogy. However, the identified gaps in technology integration, teacher confidence, and inclusive education suggest areas where improvement is needed. By addressing these gaps, the district can provide more well-rounded professional development where both teachers and learners will benefit in the process.

Table 10. *Effects of In-Service Training on the Learners (as perceived by the teachers)*

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Degree of Effect</i>
1. Improved Academic Performance	3.26	Effective	Moderately Perceived
2. Increased Engagement and Motivation	3.44	Effective	Moderately Perceived
3. Enhanced Critical Thinking Skills	3.82	Very Effective	Highly Perceived
4. Improved Classroom Behavior	3.78	Very Effective	Highly Perceived
5. Greater Use of Technology in Learning	3.76	Very Effective	Highly Perceived
6. Better Understanding of Subjects	3.64	Very Effective	Highly Perceived
7. Increased Student Confidence and Self-Efficacy	3.18	Effective	Moderately Perceived
8. Higher Levels of Student Collaboration	3.80	Very Effective	Highly Perceived
9. Improved Emotional and Social Development	3.76	Very Effective	Highly Perceived
10. Better Preparedness for Future Challenges	3.54	Very Effective	Highly Perceived
Average weighted mean	3.6	Very Effective	Highly Perceived

Table 10 reflects the effects of in-service training on the learners as perceived by the teachers. It includes the weighted mean, the interpretation and the degree of effect. As shown in the table, seven out of ten indicators are very effective as highly perceived by the teachers. It consist of the following: enhanced critical thinking skills (3.82), improved classroom behavior (3.78), greater use of technology in learning (3.76), higher levels of student collaboration (3.80), improved emotional and social development (3.76), better understanding of subjects (3.64), and better preparedness for future challenges (3.54). The result implied that in-service training programs are highly perceived to have a positive and effective impact on these aspects of student learning and development.

Three indicators are effective as moderately perceived by the teachers. It consists of the following:

Improved academic performance (3.26), the perception of INSET's impact on academic performance is moderate, which may suggest that while teachers see more improvement in student outcomes, this could be further enhanced. According to Hattie (2009), professional development that focuses on evidence-based teaching practices can have a direct impact on student achievement. Teachers who are trained in effective instructional strategies, differentiated instruction, and formative assessment are better able to meet the learning needs of their students, leading to improving academic performance. Therefore, refining the focus of INSET programs to include more targeted strategies for improving student achievement could lead to greater academic gains.

Increased engagement and motivation (3.44), engagement and motivation are essential for effective learning, and while the INSET programs are perceived to moderately influence these areas, there is potential for improvement. Fredricks et al. (2004) highlight that student engagement is multifaceted, involving behavioral, emotional, and cognitive components. Professional development that equips teachers with strategies for promoting active learning, fostering a positive classroom environment, and integrating technology can help increase student motivation and engagement. To enhance these outcomes, INSET programs could place greater emphasis on active learning approaches, student-centered pedagogy, and culturally responsive teaching practices.

Increased student confidence and self-efficacy (3.18), the moderate perception of INSET's impact on student confidence and self-efficacy suggests that while some progress is being made, there is room for improvement. Bandura's (1997) theory of self-efficacy emphasizes that students with high self-efficacy are more likely to engage in learning, persist in the face of challenges, and achieve better outcomes. Teachers who are trained to create supportive learning environments, provide constructive feedback, and encourage a growth mindset can significantly boost students' confidence. INSET programs can be improved by incorporating strategies that help teachers support the development of student self-efficacy, such as goal-setting, self-assessment, and fostering resilience.

The average weighted mean 3.6 suggests that teachers perceived in-service training programs as very effective overall. However, the moderate impact on key student outcomes- academic performance, engagement, motivation, and self-efficacy indicates a need for improvement. By refining the focus of INSET programs to strengthen instructional practices, student engagement, and self-efficacy, the Milagros district can create a more comprehensive professional development experience that not only enhances teacher skills but also significantly improves student learning performances.

Conclusions

Based from the findings of the study, the following were the conclusions drawn:

The profile of teachers in the Milagros district reveals several key findings. Firstly, the overwhelming majority of teachers are male, reflecting a trend consistent with the historical perception of teaching as predominantly male profession, majority of the ages are between 26-35, the majority of the teachers hold the positions of Teacher I or Teacher II, and were BEED graduates. Secondly, Majority of teachers have at least four years of experience in teaching. It also indicates that there is relatively small percentage of teachers with ten or more years of teaching experience, which could potentially impact the level of expertise. Thirdly, teachers have been attending Continuing Professional Development and Pedagogical training. This reflect a dedication to continuous learning and improvement among the teachers. Lastly, the majority of the teachers had an outstanding or very satisfactory performance.

The aspects of In-service training that are commonly emphasized are the Pedagogical Skills, Classroom management, Assessment and Evaluation, and Subject expertise, followed by the Professional Ethics, Curriculum Updates, Research and Innovation, Inclusive

Education, and Policy Updates. However, they appears to be a gap in the current in service training when it comes to focusing on technology and integration, as only 78% of respondents selected it as a key aspect.

When it comes to the effect of In-service Training on the Professional Growth and Development of Elementary teachers, all of the Interventions Implemented in the study were highly effective in improving various aspects of teaching and classroom management. The top three interventions, namely enhanced classroom management, better assessment practices, and improved content knowledge, were particularly successful in enhancing overall teaching skills. However, it is important to note that these interventions, even those lowest in ranked, were still considered to be effective in improving teaching practices and should have taken into consideration when implementing educational reforms.

When it comes to the effects of In-service training on the learning outcomes of learners as perceived by teachers, it is evident that the majority of teachers highly perceive 7 out of 10 indicators to be very effective. These Indicators include Enhanced Critical Thinking Skills, Improved Classroom Behaviors, Greater Use of Technology in Learning, Higher Levels of Student's Collaboration, Improved Emotional and Social Development, Better Understanding of Subjects, and Better Preparedness for future challenges. These positive results highlight the importance of implementing effective methods and strategies to support the students' development and success.

The conclusions resulted in the following recommendations:

Department of Education should implement professional development programs that cater the needs of younger teachers, focusing on advanced teaching strategies, leadership skills, and career progression to enhance their performance and job satisfaction. School heads should introduce incentives and recognition programs to motivate the teachers to pursue higher positions, this could include awards for outstanding performance, and additional responsibilities with corresponding benefits. School heads should also support and encourage the teachers to pursue advanced degrees such as Master's programs.

Elementary Schools in Milagros District should be made to bridge the gap in the emphasis on Technology and Integration, as this is an important aspect of modern education. it is important for teachers to be equipped with the necessary knowledge and skills to effectively integrate technology into their teaching methods. And it is recommended that the other important areas such as Professional Ethics, Inclusive Education, Research Innovation, Curriculum Updates, and Policy Updates, continue to be included in In-service Training Programs to ensure that teachers are well-rounded and up-to-date with current practices and policies.

Elementary Schools in Milagros District should have focus on Enhancing Teaching Skills, Adapting to Curriculum Changes, and Promoting Collaborative Teamwork among teachers. Schools should prioritize developing leadership skills and Increasing Technological Proficiency to support the implementation of these strategies. And it is important to promote Increased Confidence and self-efficacy, as well as Awareness of Inclusive Education among teachers to create a more inclusive and effective learning environment for all learners.

Elementary Schools in Milagros district should have focus on Implementing Strategies that promote enhanced Critical Thinking Skills, Improved Classroom Behavior, Greater Use of Technology in Learning, Higher Levels of Student's Collaboration, Improved Emotional and Social Development, Better Understanding of Subjects, and Better Preparedness for Future Challenges. These indicators have been highly perceived by teachers as effective and can greatly benefit students in their overall academic and personal development.

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